

NEW APPROACHES TO TEACHING AND LEARNING THROUGH ONLINE EDUCATION AND EVALUATION METHODS

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Abstract

As literacy increases in youth, the dream of acquiring university degree and getting a job in the same profession remains a constant desire of those who attend regular courses in various universities of the globe. As the world is continuously changing, the online education system and evaluation methods are also changing at the same speed in order to meet the demand and changing requirements of the aspirants or youth. Due to many constraints people not able to continue classroom-based teaching and learning and want to acquire the same amount of knowledge and experience through online education. Online learning is the greatest revolution for interested learners; otherwise, they have to pay lacks of the amount to attend a prestigious institution for traditional classroom or school-based degrees. Due to the increasing demand for online education, there is a great necessity for new approaches to improve the quality of online education in terms of student engagement and practical experience. Swayam Prabha, Swayam NPTEL, EDX are some the best online education platforms which have taken some new approaches like continuous assessment through regular assignments, quizzes, student feedback, video lecturing, and mock tests. The evaluation systems are very important to scale or know the students' knowledge they have acquired through online education and which cannot be fulfilled with a merely final examination. For the continuous evaluation, there is a great necessity of changes or new approaches in the existing online education evaluation system and which will help to make more students turn to the online education system. This paper discusses various new approaches for teaching and learning, through online education and evaluation methods with its pros and cons. Some of the new approaches for online education are ICT enabled mobile learning, animated video lecturing.

Keywords: ICT, Evaluation Methods, Mock Test, Online Education, New Approaches, Teaching and Learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

A healthy education has been a well-defined method of teaching that promotes knowledge, helps to learn, acquires unique values, beliefs or practices, and leads to a person's general personal growth. Presently, without going to visit the classroom, people can learn innovative ideas and sit anywhere and anytime or omnipresent with the aid of advanced developments in IT [1-2]. Pedagogical technology leads to increasing efficiency via its use and governance of

technological equipment or procedures or resources in a number of areas, such as learning theory, computer-based education, online learning and m-learning [3-5]. In classroom based education system means that students don't even have the right to change the content of the curriculum or topic instantly and that teacher passes knowledge to students of a constrained classroom. Mobile teaching or m-learning is not effective or successful due to various constraints, such as: (1) small screen size, (2) low teachings quality; (3) limited teaching bandwidth, (4) high communication expenses, (5) poor learning and certificate methods; (6) lack of technical capabilities, (7) lack of integrated room and unavailability of one-to - one communication or verbal communication. As the world is changing constantly, online education and evaluation procedures are changing at the same speed to fulfill the changing requirements of the aspirants or teenagers. Due to many constraints, people could not continue teaching and learning based on the classroom or traditional learning and wants to learn the very same amount of information and experience through online training.

There is a high necessity of new approaches to teaching and learning to overcome the existing problems of online education system. In this way massive open online courses are introduced like EDX, NPTEL, SWAYAM, and these portals have made online education dynamic and active through video sessions and

2. EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY

Technology in education is service concepts like technology in transport, technology in services with the aid of special hardware, software, or system which improves the overall performance or effectiveness of education [6-8]. A good Education is a well-defined process of acquiring skills, facilitating learning, obtaining special values, beliefs or habits, which results in overall individual growth of a person. Nowadays a student can learn new concepts without actually visiting the traditional classroom and sitting anywhere, anytime, or ubiquitously with the aid of advanced developments in Information and communication technology. Normally educational technology can be classified as Hardware approach, Software approach, Systems approach. Hardware approach uses some special physical equipment like microphone, which is essential to make voice audible to a big crowd or audience and helps the teacher to make his teaching very effective. In these context audio-visual aids such as slides, charts, models, graph, and some of the electronic gadgets like radio, television, filmstrips, projectors, video, and high-speed computers are successfully used in order deliver educational contents to the audience or students and to make the teaching very effective. The second type of educational technology is mainly based on behavioral sciences and this type of technology adopt process based techniques with an ultimate intention to produce high-quality teaching-learning content or material, special teaching or learning strategies or assessment technologies. The third type of educational technology is based on computer engineering and usually referred to like the system. Educational Technology is usually classified into two as;

1. Technology of Education
2. Technology in Education

3. TECHNOLOGY OF EDUCATION

It is inherent or natural in education itself which is not derived or exported from any external source. It refers to behavioral science and applications of teaching and learning practices used

by the teacher to deliver the content in more understandable way to students. It focuses on solving the educational problems and the different techniques used in teaching learning problems with an ultimate goal to make the students understandable in more effective and easily [9-12]. Not only the teaching but also the techniques of planning, financing, and administration are also included in technology of education. Techniques of curriculum planning, teaching, learning, and evaluating also come under technology of education. The technology of education generally includes or covers following techniques;

Planning and Analysis or Examination of Instructional problems

- Selection of instrument or process or special methods for evaluation
- The various strategies adopted to obtain desired result from the teaching learning process.
- The behavior of the teacher
- Programmed learning techniques
- System analysis

4. TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION

Technology in education involves the use of special implements, tools, machines, or computer systems as like we use these for the cultivation and development of agriculture, industry, or day to day life with an intension to reduce human interaction and to fill the gap between scientific technology and education. Technology in education includes electronic media projector, film, radio, teaching machine, computer, TV and Internet. Technology in education is the application of engineering principles and various types of technologies which work together to attain some goals in education. The origin of technology in education lies in physical science or engineering principles, whereas technology of education lies in behavioral science. The table 1 shows differences between Technology of education and Technology in education.

Table 1: Differences between Technology of Education and Technology in Education

Areas	Technology of Education	Technology in Education
1. Basis	Based on the physiological behavior of the teacher.	Based on the principles of physical science and engineering technology and smart machines
2. Approach	The approach is usually logical in nature and also can be identified as software approach	The approach is physical in nature which we can see and feel and also can be identified as hardware approach
3. Origin	Its origin is based on application of behavior science based problems	Its origin is based on physical science and engineering to education.

4. Examples	Textbook, Workbook, newspapers, evaluation software	TV, Projector, Computer, OHP, Filmstrips, Video, Models.
5. Relation	It's related to learning aids and which helps to improve learning efficiency.	It's related to teaching aids and which helps to improve teaching efficiency.
6. Requirement	In order to handle this approach does not require skilled persons.	In order to handle this approach require skilled persons unlike software approach
7. Flexible	This approach not more flexible in nature	This approach is more flexible in nature
8. Type	Here constructive educational technology is utilized	Here relative educational technology is utilized.
9. Application or Contribution to educational system	This approach is very helpful in understanding the need of the learners or students and educating them based on their ability	It is applicable in mass education programmes and can be reached to large audience.
10. Cost	This approach is less expensive	This approach is expensive.

5. WHY STUDENTS NEED TECHNOLOGY IN CLASSROOM?

Following are the various reasons in support of use of technology in classroom [13-14].

- Nowadays smart mobile phone comes with various applications or apps which helps and assists the students in teaching and learning process. The challenge is to monitor the usage of mobile phones because lot of non-educational contents also delivered through mobile devices.
- Integrating technology with classroom makes students all over the world single group with students of various learning styles and behaviors.
- Technology in education helps the students in team management, team building by interacting with their classmates and instructors.
- Using technology in classroom makes or builds a platform for teachers and all other types of faculty members to enhance and develop student's eco-friendly, paperless digital content development skills. At the same time usage of mobile devices monitored and controlled safely, correctly and responsible way.
- Integrating technology with education makes the students more engaged because all the students' community has been engaged in using mobile phones most of the time.
- Integrating or combining classroom with virtual reality is a live example to demonstrate how the technology influences and enhances the teaching learning experience of both students and teachers and creates new opportunities.

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- Through Wi-Fi enabled classroom and mobile technology students can able to access most updated information
 - Through the adoption technology in education traditional passive learning model is vanished and teacher becomes only encourager, guide or a coach.
 - Technology helps the students to become more creative, interactive, responsible, and connected.

6. CUSTOMIZED AND UBIQUITOUS MOBILE LEARNING (CUML)-SYSTEM

The system has four components as Server (video lecturing provider), Client (Learners), Content Provider Engine and Sensor Network. Each component has different tasks.

Server

This component provides permission or privilege to video lecturing provider to access CUML-system services. It permits authorized video lecturing provider to upload the video classes' content, SMS and send announcements using WiMax.

Client (Learner)

This component is related to the registered learners who have privileges to use the system. The learner can connect to server in order to access multi disciplinary subject's video lecturing classes. Following are the some important function of client component.

- Once registration is approved by the server, learner can login to the CUML system with valid user name and password.
- Receive the SMS from server informing new video lecturing class in respective field
- Learner can request for video lecturing class which includes duration of 1hour or more in multi disciplinary subjects
- User can change the password whenever required
- Learners can give feed back to the video lecturing class provider through server.
- Learners can discuss about particular video lecturing class through server.

Content Provider Engine

This component is useful, when the server is not able to find video lecturing class file requested by the client, server passes this request to content provider engine. Content provider engine search for the file in Web and finds the file. The new file is stored in database, so that when user requests for the same file, server process the request by retrieving the file from its database. Following are the some important function of content provider engine component.

- Successfully search the video lecturing class file from the web, when server is not able to locate.
- Store the new content in server local database

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- Provide the content in one standard version or format.

Sensor Network

This component is used to automatically sense the user personal and environmental situations. Following are the some important function of Sensor Network component.

- Identify the learner's location so that location specific video lecturing is provided to user
- On-body sensor can identify level of heartbeat and blood pressure in order to provide some video lecturing class related to that
- Environmental sensor includes temperature, humidity and air ingredients using that system is able to find situations or parameters around the sensor and to provide specific video information to user.

7. LOCATION BASED ADAPTIVE MOBILE LEARNING–SYSTEM

Location information of the user is highly important data in Location Based Adaptive Mobile Learning (LBAML). This can be one of the key attributes to change the content of a material or to add more information to the already existing content. In this model, we will be using GPS device, especially GPS receiver to track the geographical position of the user and to provide content based on this data. The task of the GPS receiver is to track latitude, longitude and altitude coordinates of the user, who is trying to access the content of the respective material. Once the location sent by the particular user is processed by the server, he will be able to access modified content of the material from geographically dispersed locations. One user can select more than one location at the time of registration. In registration process the user has to register location information along with his/her personal information. The user gets access to material after evaluating User-id, password and location information. The important information about the user like username, password, location information and other personal information's are stored in a cloud database. The system has four components as Server, Client (Learner), Location Tracking System and Content Provider Engine. Each component has different functions

8. CONCLUSION

M-learning provides great flexibility and freedom for the learners to lean anytime, anywhere, without any restrictions to physical barrier. The learning utilizes different hardware and software technologies and there is complete freedom of the learners to exist different location than the teacher. The evaluation systems are very important to scale or know the students' knowledge they have acquired through online education and which cannot be fulfilled with a merely final examination. For the continuous evaluation, there is a great necessity of changes or new approaches in the existing online education evaluation system and which will help to make more students turn to the online education system. This paper discussed various new approaches for teaching and learning, through online education and evaluation methods with its pros and cons.

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